

The Variation of Solvation of Ions with Temperature in Aqueous Solutions from Conductance Data*

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The present position of the dependence of hydration of ions on temperature has been briefly reviewed. Calculation of hydration of ions from conductance data shows that the volume of the hydrated ionic shell, i.e. of the solvodynamic unit involved in electrical transport, increases with rise in temperature. This increase is almost negligible for highly hydrated ions like Li^+ , Na^+ , and Cs^{2+} etc., but is quite appreciable for the less-hydrated ions like K^+ , Rb^+ , Ca^+ , Cl^- , Br^- , and I^- etc., which leads one to infer that the primary solvation does not appreciably change but the primary hydration shell (i.e. the solvodynamic unit) expands slightly with rise in temperature. This fact may be used to explain the temperature dependence of the transport number of some common ions in aqueous solutions.

Until a few years ago, the general impression was that the hydration of ions decreased with rise in temperature¹. This is the first impression which one gets because of the more violent thermal effects on the ion-associated water molecules at higher temperatures. Some experimental evidence suggesting a larger hydration of ions at higher temperatures has, however, been accumulating in the past ten years or so. For example, the partial molal heat capacity of the solute², apparent ionic heat capacity at infinite dilution³, apparent ionic volumes⁴, values of the coefficient 'B' of the Jones and Dole viscosity equation⁵, and the decrease of Walden's product⁶, $\lambda_0\eta_0$, with rise in temperature, all point to an increase in hydration of ions at higher temperatures. It is proposed to examine this problem in more details with the help of the available conductance data using the procedure suggested by Robinson and Stokes⁷ and used earlier for studying the solvation in some protic and aprotic solvents⁸. The method is expected to provide only the primary or physical solvation¹⁰, since the water molecules attached to the ions by secondary solvation are left behind during electrical conductance.

Procedure.—The radius R_s of a hydrated ion has been evaluated by the procedure mentioned earlier⁷ although a slight modification to the original method, used here, has been proposed by Nightingale⁹. The volume V_s of the solvated ion is then $(4/3)\pi R_s^3$. Since only

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1. Bookris and Conway, "Modern Aspects of Electrochemistry", Butterworths Publications, London, 1954, p. 94.

2. Gupta *et al.*, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 160.

3. Eigen and Wicke, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1951, 55, 364.

4. Wicke *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.* (Frankfurt), 1954, 1, 340.

5. Kaminsky, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 177.

6. Nightingale, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 1364.

7. "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths Publications, London, 1959, pp. 124-26.

8. Gopal and Hussain, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 981.

9. Bookris and Conway, *Quart. Rev.*, 1949, 3, 173.

¹⁰ The two procedures do not show any appreciable difference in the values of V_s ; hence the original method has been followed here.

the changes in V_s are of interest in the present context, solvation numbers have not been calculated. The values of V_s for different ions at different temperatures are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Ion.	V_s (in Å ³) at temperature of							
	0°.	5°.	15°.	25°.	35°.	45°.	55°.	100°.
Li ⁺	217	218	219	218	210	218	218	234
Na ⁺	128	134	138	143	144	147	149	168
K ⁺	49	52	56	62	67	72	76	91
Rb ⁺	42	45	50	55	60	64	69	..
Ag ⁺	78	..	..	91	..	..	..	144
NH ⁺	51	..	..	62	66	..	..	106
Cl ⁻	44	51	54	57	60	64	67	76
Br ⁻	44	46	50	54	57	61	64	..
I ⁻	47	48	52	56	61	63	67	..
Ca ²⁺	290	..	291	296	300	302	..	304
Ba ²⁺	249	..	..	276	..	..	..	284
Mg ²⁺	299	..	..	324	..	..	..	327
La ³⁺	367	..	..	373	..	..	..	366

Considering the changes in the values of V_s , shown in Table I, within the temperature range, say, 25° to 55°, in which most of the experimental investigations are usually carried out, two important conclusions may be drawn. Firstly, V_s of an ion appears to increase with rise in temperature and secondly, the increase is much more marked in the less-solvated ions, which is made more explicit in Table II.

TABLE II

Ion.	% Increase in V_s per degree at 25-55°.	Ion.	% Increase in V_s per degree at 25-55°.	Ion.	% Increase in V_s per degree at 25-55°.
Li ⁺	0.00	K ⁺	0.77	Cl ⁻	0.53
Na ⁺	0.13	Rb ⁺	0.83	Br ⁻	0.55
Ca ²⁺	0.10	NH ₄ ⁺	0.00	I ⁻	0.53

The increase in the volume of the primary hydration shell may be due to an increase in the concentration of single water molecules as the result of the rise in temperature¹⁰. It is difficult, however, to see, how this is possible since the primary solvation is a saturation effect holding the maximum number, independent of temperature, of water molecules. The appreciable increase in V_s of the larger less-hydrated ions, in which water molecules are held with weaker forces, and an almost negligible rise in the smaller highly hydrated ions with strong ion-solvent interaction appear to show that the primary hydration shell expands as a result of the rise in temperature although the effect of some structural changes should not be totally ruled out (for example, the effective volume of the water molecules increases due to fall in density). In view of the fact that the release of water molecules at higher temperatures should encourage only loose secondary solvation, the shell-expansion concept appears to be more in accord with the observations. So the conclusion of some

workers¹⁰ that the primary solvation is temperature-independent seems to be justified from the analysis of the conductance data. The deduction that the decrease in $\lambda_{0.70}$ at higher temperatures indicates larger hydration, appears to be unsatisfactory. The primary hydration remains unchanged; only the volume of the primary hydration shell increases slightly when the temperature rises. It is possible that the conclusion of the increase in solvation with rise in temperature, arrived at from the static methods²⁻⁴ measuring total hydration (primary and secondary), may still be justified because the secondary hydration may increase on account of the increase in the concentration of the single water molecules at higher temperatures.

Primary Hydration and Transport Number of Ions.—The variation of V_s with temperature should explain the variation of the transport number of an ion with temperature because, other factors being common the velocity of the ion should be inversely proportional to its radius R_s in solution. Taking the same anion, say, the chloride ion, this fact explains the smaller transport numbers of Li^+ , Na^+ , Cu^{2+} etc. as compared to those of K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , etc. Also the primary hydration shell of ions like Li^+ , Na^+ , and Ca^{2+} increases only inappreciably with rise in temperature, whereas opposite is the case with ions like K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Cl^- , Br^- , and I^- . This may explain the decrease in the transport number of a halide ion and an increase in that of any one of the counter ions like Li^+ , Na^+ , and Ca^{2+} , forming the electrolyte, with rise in temperature. The hitherto so-called anomalous position of K^+ ion in KCl , as regards its transport number, can also be explained on similar grounds. As is well known, the transport number of K^+ in potassium chloride, although less than 0.5, decreases with rise in temperature. This is against the general rule of Kohlrausch¹¹, according to which the transport numbers of ions approach 0.5 with rise in temperature. Since volume V_s of K^+ ion rises more rapidly than of Cl^- ion (or any other halide ion) when the temperature is raised (see Table II), the transport number of K^+ in KCl (or in any of its halides) must decrease with rise in temperature. The same behaviour should be expected of Rb^+ and Cs^+ ions in their respective halides.

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